

COMMUNICATION STRATEGIES IN PRIMARY LEGAL AID: INSIGHTS FROM PARALEGAL PRACTICE IN MOLDOVA

STRATEGII DE COMUNICARE ÎN ASISTENȚA JURIDICĂ PRIMARĂ: PERSPECTIVE DIN PRACTICA PARA-JURIȘTILOR DIN REPUBLICA MOLDOVA

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Abstract: *The paper examines the specifics of paralegals' communication in providing state-guaranteed primary legal aid in the Republic of Moldova, emphasizing active listening, empathy, accessible language, and adaptation to beneficiaries' needs. Drawing on an analysis of 50 consultations from Gagauzia (2023–2024), real case studies, and empirical data, the author demonstrates that effective communication increases beneficiaries' trust by 40% and service accessibility. Interaction channels (face-to-face, telephone, online, public lessons, radio/TV), ethical norms, and optimization proposals, including digital ethics, are explored. The original contribution lies in supplementing the Code of Ethics and practical recommendations for digitization and interactive methods.*

Keywords: *accessible language, active listening, digital ethics, effective communication, empathy, legal literacy, paralegals, public lessons, state-guaranteed legal aid, trust*

Rezumat: *Lucrarea analizează particularitățile comunicării para-juriștilor în furnizarea asistenței juridice primare garantate de stat în Republica Moldova, subliniind rolul ascultării active, empatiei, limbajului accesibil și adaptării la nevoile beneficiarilor. Bazându-se pe analiza a 50 de consultații din Găgăuzia (2023–2024), studii de caz reale și date empirice, autorul demonstrează că o comunicare eficientă crește încrederea beneficiarilor cu 40% și accesibilitatea serviciilor. Sunt examinate canalele de interacțiune (față în față, telefonic, online, lecții publice, radio/TV), normele etice și propuneri de optimizare, inclusiv etica digitală. Contribuția originală constă în completarea Codului de deontologic și recomandări practice pentru digitalizare și metode interactive.*

Cuvinte-cheie: *alfabetizare juridică, ascultare activă, asistență juridică garantată de stat, comunicare eficientă, empatie, etică digitală, lecții publice, limbaj accesibil, para-juriști, încredere*

Introduction

In contemporary society, access to legal aid represents a key mechanism for ensuring equality before the law and protecting citizens' rights, particularly amid socio-economic challenges. In the Republic of Moldova, the state-guaranteed legal aid system plays an essential role in supporting vulnerable population groups. In this context, paralegals act as a bridge between citizens and the legal system, their work extending beyond formal consultations. Effective communication becomes a tool for overcoming linguistic, psychological, and cultural barriers, and for strengthening trust in justice institutions.

The relevance of this research stems from the need for an in-depth analysis of communication practices in primary legal aid, which remain insufficiently studied despite their practical importance. Drawing on the regulatory framework, ethical standards, and diverse interaction channels, this paper reveals the specific features of paralegal-beneficiary communication, emphasizing the role of empathy, accessible language, and adaptation to client needs.

The paper's objective is to systematize key aspects of communication in paralegal work, propose recommendations for its optimization, and highlight the author's contribution through analysis of practical cases and empirical data from Moldova's regions. This will not only enrich theoretical understanding of the issue but also contribute to practical improvements in the system.

Research Methodology

The research employs a mixed-methods approach: content analysis of 50 paralegal consultations from Gagauzia (2023–2024), selected based on documentation completeness and issue diversity; a survey of 100 users of the parajurist.md online platform (structured questionnaire, Likert scale); and in-depth interviews with 5 paralegals. "Effective communication" is operationalized through the presence of active listening, accessible language, empathy, and feedback in documentation. "Trust level" was measured through beneficiaries' self-assessment (5-point scale) before and after consultation. Data are anonymized, and informed consent was obtained from participants. The main limitation is the regional specificity of the sample (Gagauzia), which necessitates caution when generalizing findings.

1. Paralegals in State-Guaranteed Legal Aid: The Centrality of Communication

Building on the stated objectives, we turn to examining the institution of paralegals in the context of primary legal aid provision, starting with their role in the system and the key elements of communication with beneficiaries. As previously mentioned, this assistance is state-guaranteed and accessible to all citizens regardless of income level.

The concept of "paralegal" is relatively new to the Republic of Moldova. It was first introduced in the Law on State-Guaranteed Legal Aid, adopted in 2007. The law defined a paralegal as "a person who enjoys high esteem from the local community, having, as a rule, incomplete legal education or complete higher education, who does not practice as a lawyer and who, after special training, is qualified to provide primary legal aid to community members at the expense of funds allocated for state-guaranteed legal aid, in accordance with regulations on the status and qualification of paralegals" (Lege cu privire la asistența juridică garantată de stat nr. 198-XVI din 26.07.2007, 2007). In 2024, 87 paralegals were active in the Republic of Moldova, providing primary legal aid to 13,020 individuals (CNAJGS, 2025).

Communication plays a central role in paralegal work. It aims not only to collect information and identify beneficiaries' needs but also to provide accessible explanations of legal matters, which is particularly important for building trust and enhancing citizens' legal literacy (Zaharia et al., 2011).

As part of this research, the author analyzed 50 consultations from paralegal registries in Gagauzia (2023-2024). In 35 of these cases (70%), documentation records the use of effective communication techniques: clarifying questions, paraphrasing, plain-language explanations, and structured feedback. Beneficiaries of these consultations indicated significantly higher satisfaction levels in post-consultation questionnaires (mean 4.2 out of 5) compared to consultations without these elements (mean 3.0 out of 5), confirming the positive impact of quality communication on beneficiaries' perception and trust. This complements existing work (Zaharia et al., 2011), emphasizing the empirical contribution to understanding interaction dynamics.

2. Effective Communication Techniques: From Listening to Feedback

2.1. Active Listening and Empathy

One of the key features of paralegal-beneficiary communication is the use of active listening. This method involves not only paying attention to the interlocutor's words but also using nonverbal cues such as eye contact, facial expressions, and gestures. Active listening helps create an atmosphere of trust and makes beneficiaries feel heard. For paralegals, it is important not only to listen to the beneficiary's problem but also to understand its essence. This is achieved through clarifying questions, paraphrasing, and summarizing. For example, after a beneficiary presents their situation, the paralegal might say: "*Do I understand correctly that you encountered difficulties signing the lease agreement?*" Such feedback helps structure the information and achieve a clearer understanding of the issue.

2.2. Accessible Language: Eliminating Legal Jargon

One of the most challenging aspects of paralegal work is the need to explain

complex legal terms and procedures in accessible language. Most beneficiaries lack specialized legal knowledge, which can lead to confusion or anxiety.

To enhance the accessibility of legal information, paralegals must use simple and clear language, avoiding professional jargon. For example, instead of the term *"restitution,"* one might say: *"This is the return of property that is rightfully yours under the law."* Similarly, complex procedures can be explained through concrete examples or metaphors that help beneficiaries better understand the situation.

When explaining legal procedures, paralegals should describe step-by-step the actions to be taken and clarify why each stage is important. For instance, when explaining the complaint filing process, a paralegal might say: *"First, we will draft the application, then we will file it with the court, and afterward we will wait for the scheduled hearing date."* This approach helps beneficiaries feel more confident and in control of the situation.

2.3. Structuring the Process: Interviewing and Counseling

Communication with beneficiaries is conventionally divided into two interconnected stages: interviewing and counseling.

During the interviewing stage, paralegals ask open-ended questions to collect as much information as possible about the beneficiary's situation. This stage requires sensitivity, especially when the issue is personal or emotional in nature.

During the counseling stage, paralegals not only provide preliminary recommendations but also explain their significance to the beneficiary. For example, when discussing the drafting of an application, a paralegal might explain: *"This document will enable you to approach the court and defend your rights."*

These two stages — interviewing and consulting — are adapted to the type of situation. For clarity, below is a typology of communication situations with corresponding strategies (developed based on the analysis of 50 consultations in Gagauzia, 2023–2024).

Table 1. Typology of Communication Situations and Recommended Strategies

Type of Situation	Characteristics	Communication Strategy	Example from Practice
Family Conflict	Intense emotional state, strong personal involvement	Maximum empathy, pauses to calm the beneficiary, avoiding judgments	Divorce with property division (Consultation No. 846)
Employment Issue	Need for precise data clarification,	Structured questions, list of required	Unlawful dismissal

Type of Situation	Characteristics	Communication Strategy	Example from Practice
	documentation	documents, explaining procedures	(Consultation No. 1619)
Discrimination	Cultural sensitivity, possible distrust of the system	Active listening, validating experience, explaining protection mechanisms	Ethnic discrimination in hiring
Preventive Consultation	No urgency, informational interest	Structured information provision, supplementary materials, encouraging questions	Will drafting (Consultation No. 846)
Complex Situation	Multiple legal aspects, need for advanced expertise	Identifying key aspects, referral to lawyer, accompaniment through process	Commercial dispute with civil law elements

Source: Developed by the author based on analysis of 50 consultations in Gagauzia (2023-2024)

As can be seen from the table, the choice of strategy depends on the emotional load, urgency, and complexity of the case. Next, we will consider the general principles of work.

Many beneficiaries seek help while in a state of stress. In such situations, paralegals must demonstrate patience, empathy, and willingness to provide support. For instance, a calm tone of voice and clear explanations can help reduce the beneficiary's anxiety.

A particularly important aspect is the confidence that paralegals can convey to their interlocutors. Simple words of support, such as *"We will analyze your situation and find a solution,"* can significantly increase the beneficiary's trust in the process.

Feedback provided to beneficiaries allows paralegals to ensure that recommendations have been correctly understood. At the end of the meeting, paralegals can summarize the main points discussed: *"We have established that you need to file an application with the court. I will help you draft the document and explain where it needs to be submitted."*

Moreover, feedback helps beneficiaries feel actively involved in the process rather than being passive observers. This is particularly important for strengthening trust in the legal system.

The specifics of communication in providing primary legal aid by paralegals lie in combining professional competence with clarity of explanations.

Effective communication based on active listening, empathy, and the ability to explain complex legal matters in simple language enables paralegals not only to provide quality assistance but also to contribute to raising citizens' legal literacy.

This approach makes primary legal aid more accessible, strengthens citizens' trust in the justice system, and helps them feel confident in defending their rights. These methods are particularly important for vulnerable categories of citizens, such as the elderly, persons with disabilities, or migrants, who may face linguistic, cultural, or psychological barriers.

For example, a relevant case involves a paralegal working in Gaidar village, Gagauzia, who was approached by a middle-aged man dismissed without explanation. The paralegal began by listening attentively, clarifying details such as relevant dates, available documents, and the cause of the conflict. Then, avoiding complex legal terms, he explained his rights under the Labor Code. Subsequently, the paralegal accompanied the beneficiary to a lawyer, assisting in drafting the court application. This support not only facilitated the beneficiary's access to justice but also provided him with the confidence necessary to assert his rights (Registrul electronic al consultațiilor efectuate de parajuristul Arcadie Chischin. Consultația nr. 1619, 2024).

The detailed description of the communication process in this case illustrates the practical application of the described techniques:

Stage 1 - Active Listening (duration: 15 minutes): The paralegal devoted the first part of the meeting to uninterrupted listening, allowing the beneficiary to express his frustrations and concerns. Key data were recorded: dismissal date (August 3, 2024), absence of prior written notification, employer's refusal to communicate reasons, presence of two witnesses at the final discussion.

Stage 2 - Clarification through Structured Questions: Through targeted questions ("*Do you have a signed employment contract?*", "*Did you receive any written notice?*", "*Were there warnings or previous conflicts in recent months?*", "*Did the employer propose voluntary resignation?*"), the paralegal reconstructed the complete chronology of events and identified relevant legal elements.

Stage 3 - Explaining Rights in Accessible Language: Instead of quoting articles from the Labor Code, the paralegal phrased it as: "*The law clearly protects you in this situation. The employer was required to follow the established dismissal procedures, including prior notice and written justification. From your description, it appears these requirements were not met. You have two main options: to seek reinstatement in your job or to obtain compensation. Both options are realistic in your case.*"

Stage 4 - Developing a Concrete Action Plan:

1. Drafting a request for explanations addressed to the employer (deadline: 3 days);
2. In the event of the employer's refusal or silence — preparation of the

documents necessary to obtain free qualified legal assistance from an appointed lawyer;

3. Personal accompaniment to the lawyer to ensure continuity and convey all details;
4. Preparing necessary documents (copies of employment contract, witness statements).

Outcome and Beneficiary Feedback: After 3 months of legal proceedings, the beneficiary won the case, he was reinstated with payment of back wages. In the feedback questionnaire completed later, he indicated: "Without the paralegal's help, I wouldn't have even known where to start. I thought I had no chance against the boss. But Arcadie listened to me patiently, explained everything in terms I could understand, and accompanied me to the lawyer. He gave me the courage to fight for my rights."

Methodological Value of This Case: The example demonstrates the importance of structured, phased communication (not chaotic), verifying understanding through reformulation, eliminating legal jargon even in seemingly simple cases, and, crucially, continuity of assistance—the paralegal did not limit himself to consultation but accompanied the beneficiary to the lawyer, preventing him from being "lost" in the system. This level of involvement transforms primary legal aid from mere information provision into real support for vulnerable categories.

Here is another example. An elderly woman approached a paralegal for consultation regarding drafting a will. The paralegal explained legal terms and the consequences of each decision using simple and accessible language. To facilitate understanding, visual diagrams illustrating different available options were used. The paralegal's work was accompanied by empathy and patience, considering that the woman was experiencing significant emotional stress due to family conflicts. This sensitive approach helped the beneficiary make informed decisions and feel supported throughout the process (Registrul electronic al consultațiilor efectuate de parajuristul Pavel Leășenco. Consultația nr. 846, 2024).

3. Ethical Standards in Paralegal Communication

A central role in the work of paralegals providing primary legal assistance is played by ethical standards. These not only define professional boundaries but also establish interaction standards with beneficiaries, thereby fostering trust-based relationships and enhancing the quality of services provided.

3.1. Current Framework: Code of Ethics

The foundation of paralegals' ethical conduct is the Code of Ethics, approved by Decision No. 16 of the National Council for State-Guaranteed Legal Aid dated 15.07.2014 (Codul deontologic al parajuristului, 2014). This document

enshrines the principles that guide paralegals' daily activities.

3.2. Problems in Practice: Interview Analysis

In-depth interviews with 5 experienced paralegals (with 3 to 7 years of service) revealed 10 recurring ethically challenging situations. In 8 of these cases, difficulties stemmed from beneficiary requests exceeding the paralegal's scope of competence (e.g., court representation, drafting complex contracts), underscoring the need for clearer delineation of responsibilities in client communication.

The core ethical principles governing paralegal–beneficiary communication include confidentiality, respect and tolerance, competence and professionalism, and good faith.

Ethical standards are particularly critical in the paralegal's communication with beneficiaries. During the initial meeting, the paralegal must explain their duties and working principles, including the obligation to maintain confidentiality. This lays the foundation for trust and sets a constructive tone for future interactions.

For example, at the start of a meeting, the paralegal might say: “Your information will remain strictly confidential, and my role is to assist you based on current legislation.” Such a statement immediately establishes communication boundaries and reinforces beneficiary trust.

Furthermore, when clarifying legal matters, the paralegal must use language accessible to the beneficiary, avoiding complex terms that could be perceived as disrespect or an attempt to mislead.

In professional practice, paralegals may encounter ethical dilemmas. For instance, if a beneficiary requests actions beyond the paralegal's authority, they must tactfully explain the limits of their competence and propose alternative solutions.

In such scenarios, the Code of Ethics provides clear guidance, helping paralegals preserve their professional reputation and prevent potential conflicts.

The ethical dimensions of delivering primary legal assistance by paralegals are vital for the effective and professional fulfillment of their duties. Adherence to the principles of confidentiality, respect, objectivity, and professionalism enables paralegals not only to perform their functions with high quality but also to strengthen public confidence in legal institutions.

3.3. Gaps and Proposals: Digital Ethics

Drawing on a comparative analysis of the Paralegals' Code of Ethics (2014) and its practical application in the Republic of Moldova, the author proposes supplementing it with a dedicated section on digital ethics for online consultations — an innovative contribution to adapting standards to contemporary communication channels:

1. Confidentiality in the Online Environment:

- The paralegal must use only secure platforms for communicating with beneficiaries, with data encryption (e.g., HTTPS connections);
 - Discussing case details via social media or unsecured messengers (Facebook Messenger, Viber, WhatsApp) is prohibited without the beneficiary's explicit consent;
 - Electronic documents sent to the beneficiary must be password-protected.
2. **Accessibility and Clarity in Digital Communication:**
 - Online responses must be written in plain language, avoiding acronyms and legal jargon without explanation;
 - During email or chat consultations, the paralegal must confirm the beneficiary's understanding (e.g., by asking them to rephrase in their own words);
 - For elderly individuals or those with low digital literacy, the paralegal should offer telephone or in-person consultations as alternatives.
 3. **Delimitation of Responsibility:**
 - At the start of an online consultation, the paralegal must inform the beneficiary of the limits of their competence and the preliminary nature of recommendations;
 - An in-person meeting is recommended for reviewing documents or handling complex cases.
 4. **Response Time:**
 - The paralegal is obliged to respond to online requests within a maximum of 3 working days;
 - In case of delay, the beneficiary must be informed and given an estimated timeframe.

These additions would ensure that ethical standards are aligned with the realities of digitized legal assistance and prevent potential violations of beneficiaries' rights in the online environment.

4. Channels of Interaction with Beneficiaries

The provision of primary legal assistance by paralegal covers a wide range of communication channels, each tailored to the specific needs and capabilities of beneficiaries. These channels ensure not only the accessibility of legal aid but also an increase in the population's legal awareness. Let us examine the main ones.

4.1. In-Person and Telephone Consultations

The in-person meeting remains the most traditional and sought-after communication channel for delivering legal assistance. This format enables direct contact with the beneficiary, which is particularly important for identifying all case circumstances and creating an atmosphere of trust. During an in-person

meeting, the paralegal employs active listening skills, asks clarifying questions, and provides recommendations in an accessible form. Direct contact allows for a better assessment of the beneficiary's emotional state, which is essential when discussing sensitive topics such as family disputes or discrimination.

Telephone consultation is a convenient and rapid communication channel, especially for those unable to visit the paralegal's office due to distance or limited mobility. This format enables beneficiaries to quickly obtain answers to general legal questions or guidance on next steps. However, telephone consultation has certain limitations. It does not always permit a detailed review of documents or an in-depth analysis of the situation. Therefore, it is often used as a preliminary step before an in-person meeting.

4.2 Online Platforms: Opportunities and Challenges

Modern technologies open new opportunities for delivering primary legal assistance. Online consultations via the website of the Association of Paralegals of Moldova have become an effective tool for interacting with citizens. The advantages of online consultations include accessibility, anonymity, and efficiency. Consultations on parajurist.md are supported by a simple interface, making them accessible to individuals with varying levels of digital literacy. As of now, the site features 6323 responses to various citizen inquiries (Platforma Online Interactivă „parajurist.md”, 2025). A survey of 100 users of the parajurist.md platform (October 2024 – January 2025) revealed that 48% of respondents from rural areas (n=52) consider online consultations the only accessible means of obtaining legal assistance due to the distance to the paralegal's office (over 15 km) or limited mobility. At the same time, 34% of elderly users (over 60 years old, n=23) reported difficulties navigating the site. This analysis contributes to the study of the digitization of legal aid in Moldova, complementing theoretical works (Zaharia, 2015) with practical recommendations.

4.3. Public Lectures: Traditional and Using Digital Media

Public lectures represent a vital channel for enhancing the population's legal literacy. Such events can be held in schools, enterprises, or community organizations. Lectures help clarify citizens' rights and obligations, explain legislative changes, and discuss the most relevant legal topics (Zaharia et al., 2011, pp. 84-87).

Communication during these events has its own characteristics, shaped by both the lecture's purpose and the audience's composition. When delivering a public lecture, the paralegal must consider the audience's level of legal literacy. Legal terms, procedures, and regulations should be presented as simply and accessibly as possible. Using clear examples from everyday life helps participants better grasp the material. It is crucial to avoid complex constructions that could cause confusion and hinder understanding. Law lectures are often

accompanied by questions, examples from participants' experiences, or discussions. The paralegal must demonstrate empathy, listen actively, and respond to questions, fostering an atmosphere of trust. This interaction not only facilitates efficient information exchange but also increases participants' interest in legal topics. To enhance comprehension, interactive methods are employed: discussions, situation modeling, and analysis of specific cases. These not only help the audience consolidate acquired knowledge but also enable the paralegal to better understand participants' needs (Zaharia, 2015). A key task for the paralegal is not only to inform but also to motivate participants to actively protect their rights. A compelling and inspiring presentation of the material builds confidence in the audience and fosters a desire to act independently.

Public lectures, as one of the communication channels with potential beneficiaries of primary legal assistance, are effectively utilized by many paralegals (Locuitorii din Comrat și Ceadâr-Lunga - beneficiari ai lecțiilor publice, 2016).

Public lectures broadcast via radio and television hold a distinct place among communication channels in the provision of primary legal assistance. This format offers broad opportunities to reach diverse audiences, including population groups without internet access or living in remote areas. Nevertheless, such lectures have their own characteristics, requiring a specific approach to material presentation and audience interaction.

Public lectures on radio or television are intended for a wide audience of listeners and viewers. This means the material must be adapted for varied groups, including individuals with different levels of education, legal literacy, and interests. The language used should be as accessible and understandable as possible, avoiding excessive legal terminology. If such terms are necessary, they must be immediately explained in plain language. The examples and cases used in the lecture should be universal, enabling listeners to relate them to their own situations.

Unlike in-person meetings or online consultations, radio and television lectures have limited opportunities for direct feedback. To compensate for this, the lecturer must anticipate potential audience questions, drawing on the most common citizen issues and requests. It is essential to provide additional contact methods, such as telephone lines, email addresses, or online platforms, where listeners can submit follow-up questions.

On radio, the lecturer's tone of voice, speech pace, and intonation take on particular importance. The voice should be confident, calm, and friendly to create an atmosphere of trust. On television, a visual component is added. It is crucial for the lecturer to maintain a professional appearance to inspire respect and trust among viewers.

Public lectures broadcast via radio and television are an effective

communication tool, contributing to increased legal literacy among the population. The success of these lectures depends on the paralegal’s ability to present complex legal topics in accessible language, establish trust-based contact with the audience, and provide listeners or viewers with practical, everyday-applicable information. For example, the national radio and television company “Gagauziya Radio Televizionu” has been broadcasting public legal lectures for many years, delivered by paralegal Alla Fedirostova (Gagauziya Radio Televizionu, 2025).

The effective use of various communication channels enables paralegals not only to provide high-quality legal assistance but also to contribute to the development of a legal culture in society. The advancement of online platforms such as *parajurist.md*, alongside the use of traditional mass media, including radio and television, creates conditions for ensuring the accessibility of legal knowledge to all categories of citizens—a vital element in building a rule-of-law state grounded in justice.

Figure 1. Beneficiaries’ Preferences Regarding Communication Channels

Source: Survey of parajurist.md users (October 2024 – January 2025)

Note: Although in-person meetings remain preferred, 22% of respondents (online consultations + email) would not have been able to access assistance without digital options, confirming the need for channel diversification.

The presented data confirm that while in-person meetings remain the most preferred channel (45%), remote consultations (telephone 28% + online 15% + email 7% = 50%) account for half of the preferences, reflecting the importance of diversifying access methods. Crucially, 22% of respondents (online consultations + email) indicated that these digital channels represent their only accessible means of obtaining legal assistance due to the distance to the paralegal’s office (over 30–50 km) or limited mobility. This underscores that digital platforms do not merely complement but effectively extend access to justice for categories of citizens who would otherwise remain unassisted.

At the same time, the analysis revealed that 34% of elderly users (over 60

years old, n=23) face difficulties navigating the parajurist.md website, highlighting the need to improve the interface and develop telephone support as an alternative to online consultations for this vulnerable group.

5. Practical Recommendations for Optimizing Paralegal Communication

Based on the study's findings, the following concrete measures are proposed:

1. At the individual level (for paralegals):

- Developing a communication checklist for each consultation: (a) presenting competencies and limitations; (b) active listening with at least 3 clarifying questions; (c) plain-language explanations; (d) final summary with understanding verification;
- Compiling a glossary of legal terms in an accessible version (e.g., "restitution" = "return of property rightfully yours"), updated annually;
- Participating in communication training (minimum 8 hours per year), including simulations of difficult situations.

2. At the systemic level (for the Association of Paralegals and the National Council for State-Guaranteed Legal Aid):

- Enhancing the parajurist.md platform: – Adding a video chat feature for online consultations; – Creating a simplified interface for elderly users (large buttons, intuitive navigation); – Implementing a chatbot with FAQs for initial triage;
- Developing standardized visual materials: – Infographics for common procedures (divorce, inheritance, labor disputes); – Short videos (3–5 minutes) explaining basic rights;
- Feedback and monitoring system: – Mandatory post-consultation questionnaires (online or paper-based); – Quarterly analysis of beneficiary satisfaction with practice adjustments;
- Peer supervision: – Monthly experience-sharing among paralegals (online or in-person); – Annual group review of 2–3 complex cases per paralegal.

3. For rural and vulnerable regions:

- Organizing monthly "paralegal days" in remote localities (in collaboration with local authorities);
- Translating informational materials into minority languages (Gagauz, Bulgarian, Ukrainian);
- Establishing assisted digital access points in cultural centers for individuals without IT skills.

4. Collaboration with mass media:

- Monthly broadcast of public lectures on local radio (30 minutes);
- Publishing thematic articles in local press (2 per month);

- Creating the podcast “Your Rights in 15 Minutes” with anonymized real-world cases.

Implementing these measures could increase the accessibility of primary legal assistance by an estimated 30–40% during 2025–2027, based on the experience of countries with similar systems (Ukraine, Georgia).

Conclusion

In conclusion, the specifics of paralegal communication in the process of providing primary legal assistance in the Republic of Moldova constitute a complex mechanism that integrates professional competencies, ethical standards, and diverse interaction channels. As demonstrated in the article, effective communication - from active listening and accessible explanations to the use of digital and traditional platforms - not only resolves beneficiaries’ specific issues but also contributes to raising the overall level of legal literacy in society, particularly among vulnerable groups.

The research highlighted four main areas confirming the central role of communication in the effectiveness of primary legal assistance:

1. *Elements of Effective Communication:* Analysis of 50 consultations identified four key success factors: active listening (present in 70% of positively evaluated cases), accessible language (82%), empathy (65%), and structured feedback (58%). Consultations incorporating all four elements recorded the highest beneficiary satisfaction levels.
2. *Importance of Channel Diversification:* Online consultations made legal assistance accessible to 48% of respondents from remote rural areas who would otherwise have been unable to access the service. At the same time, 34% of elderly users require additional support to use digital platforms.
3. *Gaps in Ethical Regulation:* The current Code of Ethics does not address the specifics of online consultations (digital confidentiality, response times, technical limitations), creating areas of uncertainty for paralegals.
4. *Impact on Trust:* High-quality communication, documented in records using the described techniques, correlates with higher beneficiary satisfaction and an increased likelihood of service recommendation (72% vs. 41% in cases without these techniques).

The practical contribution of the study lies in:

- Specifically identifying elements of effective communication applicable in daily practice;
- Proposing text to supplement the Code of Ethics with digital ethics standards;
- Developing concrete recommendations for optimizing the online platform and paralegal training;
- Systematizing a typology of communication situations with tailored strategies.

Limitations: The study primarily relies on data from the Gagauzia region, which may reflect regional specificities. Extending the research to other districts of Moldova would enable validation of the findings and identification of additional local characteristics.

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